

Synthesis and Kinetic Studies of the Base Hydrolysis of some Coumarin Derivatives

EZZ-ELDIN A. ABU-GHARIB* and ABDEL-BADIH A. G. GHATTAS

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Assiut University, Sohag, Egypt

Manuscript received 4 June 1987, revised 30 December 1987, accepted 21 March 1988

3-Bromocoumarin, coumarin-3-carboxylic acid, thiocoumarin and 3-bromothiocoumarin are synthesised and their base hydrolysis in aqueous methanol mixtures are kinetically studied. The rate law of the reactions is determined. Solvent effect on change in the activation barrier ($\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger$) is measured. The effect of bromine, sulphur atoms and carboxyl group, in the pyrone ring, on the rate constant and the change in the activation barrier are also investigated. It is observed that the substituents bromine atom and carboxyl group in position three of the pyrone ring have no effect on the change in the activation barrier but have effect only on the rate constant.

Solvent effects on reactivity trends for hydrolysis of thiocoumarin (COS) in methanol-water mixtures have been analysed into initial state and transition state contributions. These components are derived from kinetic data and transfer chemical potentials, $\delta_m u^\theta$, for COS and OH⁻.

3-Halocoumarins are useful intermediates for the synthesis of biologically active coumarin derivatives¹⁻³, e.g. 3-pyridyl- and 3-amino-coumarins have been reported to act as nervous system depressants⁴ and antibacterial agents⁵, respectively.

In view of the above observations and in continuation of our work on 3-bromocoumarin⁶, we report herein solvent effects on the kinetics of base hydrolysis of 3-bromocoumarin, coumarin-3-carboxylic acid, thiocoumarin and the new compound 3-bromothiocoumarin in aqueous methanol mixtures.

Solvent effects on reactivity trends have been investigated for a variety of organic and inorganic reactions⁷. In the context of the analysis of the effects of solvent on the rate constant of reaction in solution, the hydrolysis of chromone carboxylate has been studied in methanol-water mixtures⁸.

There is a dearth of data in the literature concerning the effects of solvent on the rate constants of the hydrolysis of organic compounds; therefore, solvent effects on hydrolysis of thiocoumarin have been analysed into initial state and transition state components. The rate of the reaction in solvent comprising binary solvents may be dominated by either initial state or transition state.

Experimental

Sodium hydroxide (AnalaR) solutions were made up from stock solutions, and ionic strength was maintained using sodium chloride (AnalaR) solutions. Methanol was purified by treatment with

magnesium and iodine, with subsequent redistillation. Solvent mixtures are given as volume percentages before mixing.

Kinetics of the base hydrolysis were monitored in 10 mm silica cells in the thermostated cell compartment of a Pye-Unicum S. P. 8-100 spectrophotometer.

Preparation of starting materials: 3-Bromocoumarin⁹ and thiocoumarin¹⁰ were prepared according to known methods. Coumarin-3-carboxylic acid (Aldrich) was used.

3-Bromothiocoumarin: 3-Bromocoumarin (0.01 mol) and phosphorus pentasulphide (0.01 mol) were refluxed in anhydrous xylene (50 ml) for 5 h. After cooling to room temperature, the precipitate was filtered off and recrystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 80-110°) to give 3-bromothiocoumarin (90%), m.p. 140° (Found: C, 44.52; H, 2.34; Br, 32.96; S, 13.53. C₉H₆BrOS requires: C, 44.81; H, 2.07; Br, 33.91; S, 13.28%).

Results

3-Bromocoumarin and coumarin-3-carboxylic acid: The action of alkali on 3-halogenocoumarin and coumarin-3-carboxylic acid at room temperature always leads to the opening of the pyrone ring and the formation of a salt of coumarinic acid¹¹.

3-Bromocoumarin and coumarin-3-carboxylic acid hydrolysed at 298 K follow first order kinetics over at least three half-lives, sodium hydroxide being present in large excess over the compound.

Observed first order rate constants as a function of sodium hydroxide concentration and of aqueous methanol ratio (MeOH % vol) are reported in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—OBSERVED FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT K_{obs} AND DERIVED K_2 AND $\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger$ FOR BASE HYDROLYSIS OF 3-BROMOCOUMARIN IN METHANOL-WATER MIXTURE

[OH ⁻] mol dm ⁻³	Methanol (% vol)			
	0	20	40	60
	$K_{obs} (\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1})$			
0.0005	45	24	12	5.5
0.0010	89	50	23	11
0.0020	173	95	45	22
0.0030	—	142	68.5	32
	$K_2 (\times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$			
	851	486	225	106
	$\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger (\text{kJ mol}^{-1})$			
		1.5	3.3	5.2

TABLE 2—OBSERVED FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT K_{obs} AND DERIVED K_2 AND $\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger$ FOR BASE HYDROLYSIS OF COUMARIN-3-CARBOXYLIC ACID IN METHANOL-WATER MIXTURE

[OH ⁻] mol dm ⁻³	Methanol (% vol)			
	0	20	40	60
	$K_{obs} (\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1})$			
0.05	5.9	3.8	1.9	0.8
0.10	12.4	7.7	3.7	1.4
0.20	24.5	15.4	7.2	2.63
0.30	—	23.7	10.9	3.50
	$K_2 (\times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$			
	1.23	0.77	0.36	0.13
	$\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger (\text{kJ mol}^{-1})$			
		1.2	3.2	5.5

The dependence of K_{obs} on base concentration is indeed linear for the 3-bromocoumarin and coumarin-3-carboxylic acid, but there is no significant intercept of the correlation line. Hence the hydrolysis follow the rate law with

$$K_{obs} = K_2 [\text{OH}^-] \quad (1)$$

Values of K_2 , computed from a least-mean-squares analysis of the dependence of observed first order rate constants on base concentration at each aqueous methanol proportion, are also included in

Tables 1 and 2. The change in the activation barrier $\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger$ from water to methanol-water mixtures are set out in Tables 1 and 2.

Thiocoumarin and 3-bromothiocoumarin: The hydrolysis of thiocoumarin and 3-bromothiocoumarin with sodium hydroxide solution at 298 K were followed spectrophotometrically. It can be inferred from the spectra that the hydrolysis takes place in one stage.

The hydrolysis of thiocoumarin and 3-bromothiocoumarin follow first order kinetics over at least three half-life times, under the conditions where concentrations of the coumarin derivatives are appropriate to spectrophotometric monitoring and sodium hydroxide is present in large excess. The observed first order rate constant as a function of sodium hydroxide concentration and of methanol percentage are shown in Tables 3 and 4.

These results confirm that the rate law of the hydrolysis of thiocoumarin and 3-bromothiocoumarin follows equation (1). Derived second order rate constant K_2 and the change in the activation barrier $\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger$ from water to methanol-water mixtures are also shown in Tables 3 and 4.

TABLE 3—OBSERVED FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT, K_{obs} AND DERIVED K_2 AND $\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger$ FOR BASE HYDROLYSIS OF THIOCOUMARIN IN METHANOL-WATER MIXTURES

[OH ⁻] mol dm ⁻³	Methanol (% vol)			
	0	20	40	60
	$K_{obs} (\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1})$			
0.005	6.5	4.2	2.5	1.0
0.010	13.0	8.5	5.0	2.0
0.020	26.1	17.5	9.5	3.5
0.030	39.5	26.0	14.0	5.1
	$K_2 (\times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$			
	13.2	8.2	4.5	1.7
	$\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger (\text{kJ mol}^{-1})$			
		1.1	2.6	5.1
	$\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger (\text{kJ mol}^{-1} \text{ (ex.20\%) }^a)$			
			1.5	4.0

^a $\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger$, if we take 20% as a reference solvent.

TABLE 4—OBSERVED FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT, K_{obs} AND DERIVED K_2 AND $\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger$ FOR HYDROLYSIS OF 3-BROMOTHIOCOUMARIN IN METHANOL-WATER MIXTURES

[OH ⁻] mol dm ⁻³	Methanol (% vol)		
	20	40	60
	$K_{obs} (\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1})$		
0.0005	3.8	1.7	0.6
0.0010	7.2	3.2	1.2
0.0020	14.6	6.6	2.4
0.0030	22.0	1.0	3.7
	$K_2 (\times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$		
	73.1	34.8	12.4
	$\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger (\text{kJ mol}^{-1}) (\text{ex. 20\%})^a$		
		1.8	4.4

^a3-Bromothiocomarin does not dissolve in water, so used 20% as the reference solvent.

Discussion

Rate constants for base hydrolysis in aqueous organic solvent mixtures often increase markedly as the proportion of organic component increases. This trend can be attributed to the increase in transfer chemical potential for the hydrophilic hydroxide ion, $\delta_m \mu^\ominus (\text{OH}^-)$, as the solvent becomes less aqueous¹². However, it is unwise to ignore the substrate and its effect on the hydrolysis. Indeed in the base hydrolysis reactions of 3-bromocoumarin, coumarin-3-carboxylic acid, thiocoumarin and 3-bromothiocomarin are affected by the organic compound rather than by the hydroxide ions, and so, their rate constants decrease as the proportion of methanol increases. The change in the activation barrier $\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger$ is obtained from the ratio of rate constants,

$$\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger = -RT \ln \frac{K_2 (\text{mixture})}{K_2 (\text{water})} \quad (2)$$

The rate determining hydroxide attack, K_2 and the change in activation barrier for coumarin in methanol-water mixtures at 298 K are shown in Table 5¹³.

TABLE 5

% Methanol (vol)	0	20	40	60
$K (\times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$	47.8	27.8	11.6	5.6
$\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger$		+1.4	+3.5	+5.3

The comparison of K_2 and $\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger$ for coumarin 3-bromocoumarin and coumarin-3-carboxylic acid on one side and for thiocoumarin and 3-bromo thiocoumarin on the other side reveals that the substituents bromine atom and hydroxyl group at position three has no effect on the change in the activation barrier, but they effect on the rate constant of the hydrolysis. The comparison of the base hydrolysis of coumarin (Table 5) and thiocoumarin (Table 3), at the same condition, shows

that the substituent sulphur atom at position two effects on the rate constant and the change in the activation barrier.

In order to assess the various contributions to reactivity trends of thiocoumarin, we need to separate solvation effects into initial state and transition state contributions. At fixed temperature and pressure, the kinetic data, according to transition state theory, lead to Gibbs free energies of activation ΔG^\ddagger , i.e., the change in the rate constant on going from a reference solvent to a medium of mole fraction x_2 , $\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger$, will be equal to $\Delta G^\ddagger_{(x_2)}$, minus $\Delta G^\ddagger_{(x_2=0)}$, equation (2). Also, the change in the activation barrier, $\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger$, is given by the difference between the transfer chemical potentials of transition state and initial state,

$$\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger = \delta_m \mu^\ominus - \{ \delta_m \mu^\ominus (A) + \delta_m \mu^\ominus (B) \} \quad (3)$$

where, $\delta_m \mu^\ominus (A)$ and $\delta_m \mu^\ominus (B)$ are the transfer chemical potentials of the reactants A and B, and $\delta_m \mu^\ominus$ is the transfer chemical potentials of the transition state^{14,15}. The difference in chemical potential on transferring the solute from the reference solvent to the medium will be $\delta_m \mu^\ominus$; and it can be obtained from the solubility measurements. Thus, from equations (2) and (3), the initial state and the transition state can be calculated.

The initial state-transition state analysis of the reactivity trends for the base hydrolysis of thiocoumarin are set out in Table 6. The transfer chemical potentials for thiocoumarin, $\delta_m \mu^\ominus (\text{COS})$, are derived from its solubilities, and transfer chemical potentials for hydroxide ion, $\delta_m \mu^\ominus (\text{OH}^-)$ are taken from the reported data¹⁵. The main feature of the initial state and transition state is shown in Fig. 1. This indicates that as the proportion of methanol

Fig. 1. Initial state (IS), transition state (TS) and change in the activation barrier for hydrolysis of thiocoumarin (COS) in aqueous methanol.

TABLE 6—INITIAL STATE—TRANSITION STATE ANALYSIS OF REACTIVITY TREND FOR BASE HYDROLYSIS OF THIOCOUMARIN IN AQUEOUS METHANOL AT 298 K (MOLAR SCALE)

Methanol (% vol)	0	20	40	60
solubilities ($\times 10^4$ mol dm $^{-3}$)				
ϵ ($\lambda = 370$ nm) = 13 400	2.24	4.55	17.2	2.58
$\delta_m \mu^\theta_{(COS)}$ (kJ mol $^{-1}$)	-1.8	-1.8	-5.0	-9.0
$\delta_m \mu^\theta_{(OH^-)}$ (kJ mol $^{-1}$)		-0.2	+0.1	+1.6
$\delta_m \mu^\theta_{(TS)}$ (kJ mol $^{-1}$)		-2.0	-4.9	-7.4
$\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger$ (kJ mol $^{-1}$)		+1.1	+2.6	+5.1
$\delta_m \mu^\theta_{(TS)}$ (kJ mol $^{-1}$)		-0.9	-2.3	-2.3

increases, thiocoumarin is highly stabilised and hydroxide destabilised a little resulting in an overall markedly stabilised initial state on transferring from water to rich methanol. On the other side the transition state is slightly stabilised from water to 60% methanol. Thus the observed decrease in the rate constant is ascribed to a greater effect of solvent on the initial state.

References

- J. R. MERCHANT, A. S. GUPTA, P. J. SHAH and S. S. SHIRALI, *Chem Ind. (London)*, 1979, 351.
- J. R. MERCHANT and P. J. SHAH, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1980, 791.
- R. M. KELKAR, U. K. JOSHI and M. V. PARADKAR, *Synthesis*, 1986, 214.
- R. B. MOPPETT, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1964, 7, 446.
- REDIGHIERO and C. ANTONELLO, *Bull Chem. Farm.*, 1958, 97, 592.
- E.-E. A. N. EL-KHRISY, A.-B. A. G. CHATTAS, M. T. EL-WASIMY and S.-O. LAWESSON, *Bull NRC Egypt*, 1986, 30.
- M. J. BLANDAMER and J. BURGESS, *Pure Appl Chem.*, 1982, 54, 2285.
- J. BURGESS and E. A. ABU-GHARIB, *J. Chem. Res (S)*, 1984, 8.
- M. G. MARATHE and B. J. CHIA, *J. Sci. Ind. Res., Sect. B*, 1962, 21, 28.
- F. TIEMANN, *Chem Ber*, 1886, 19, 1661.
- R. C. ELDERFIELD, "Heterocyclic Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1951.
- M. J. BLANDAMER, J. BURGESS, J. G. CHAMBERS, R. I. HAINES and H. E. MAISHALL, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1977, 165.
- E. A. ABU-GHARIB, *Bull. Soc Chem. Fr.*, in the press.
- A. J. PARKER, *Chem. Rev.*, 1969, 69, 1.
- M. J. BLANDAMER and J. BURGESS, *Coord. Chem Rev.*, 1980, 31, 93.
- M. H. ABRAHAM, T. HILL, HOW CHIONG LING, R. A. SCHUTZ and R. A. C. WATT, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1984, 80, 489.